

Human Resource Development Techniques In Automobile Industries (A Case Study of Eicher Motors & Force Motors)

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Abstract

The role of Human resources management continues to change, technology has continued to evolve throughout the management practices. HRD programme needs the overall efforts of each and every employee in the form of its sub systems and processes. The study confirmed that the HRD subsystems like management policy on HRD, potential appraisal and Organizational Development (OD) in the top level management, goal setting, role analysis, performance appraisal, career planning and executive development for the middle level management. In the present study, qualitative study was an in-depth interview in which the qualitative data were collected from the executive or the executive of human resource division from two automotive companies - Eicher Motors & Force Motors.

Keywords:- Human resource development , Automobile Industries, HRD Climate.

Introduction: -

The automobiles in India are one of the larger markets in the world. It had previously been one of the fastest growing globally, but is currently experiencing flat or negative growth rates. India's passenger car and commercial vehicle manufacturing industry are the sixth largest in the world, with an annual production of more than 3.9 million units in 2011. Key positive factors to make an industry of automobile and its spare parts continuously growing are domestic and global demand, long-term supporting government policy to support this main industry, coordination between the government and private sectors, and all automotive-related personnel, including skilled worker as the main resource. Whereas, negative factors affecting the industry of automobile and its spare parts can also be both domestic and global demand for automobile due to free trade areas under ASEAN Economic Community (AEC) policy. The government should reconsider the country's energy plan in order to cope with the global uncertainty due to energy crisis, natural disasters to industrial estates and other secondary manufacturing bases with the production capacity close to Thailand in Southeast Asia such as Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, and Vietnam or outside Southeast Asia region such as China and India that have massive production capacity. Human beings are social beings and hardly ever live and work in isolation. We always plan, develop and manage our relations both consciously and unconsciously. The relations are the outcome of our actions and depend to a great extent upon our ability to manage our actions. From childhood each and every individual acquire knowledge and experience on understanding others and how to behave in each and every situations in life. Later we carry forward this learning and understanding in carrying and managing relations at our workplace. The whole context of Human Resource Management

revolves around this core matter of managing relations at work place.

Definitions of HRM:-

Human resources management (HRM) is a management function concerned with hiring, motivating and maintaining people in an organization. It focuses on people in organizations. Human resource management is designing management systems to ensure that human talent is used effectively and efficiently to accomplish organizational goals.

Objectives of HRM:-

1. Personnel Objectives: it is to assist employees in achieving their personal goals, at least as far as these goals enhance the individual's contribution to the organization. Personal objectives of employees must be met if they are to be maintained, retained and motivated. Otherwise employee performance and satisfaction may decline giving rise to employee turnover.

2. Functional Objectives: is to maintain the department's contribution at a level appropriate to the organization's needs. Human resources are to be adjusted to suit the organization's demands. The department's value should not become too expensive at the cost of the organization it serves.

3. Organizational Objectives: it recognizes the role of HRM in bringing about organizational effectiveness. It makes sure that HRM is not a standalone department, but rather a means to assist the organization with its primary objectives. The HR department exists to serve the rest of the organization.

4. Societal Objectives: seek to ensure that the organization becomes socially responsible to the needs and challenges of the society while minimizing the negative impact of such demands upon the organization. The failure of the organizations to use their resources for the society's benefit in ethical ways may lead to restriction.

Human Resource Development:-

Human resource development is a framework for managing, developing, and optimizing employee skills, abilities and competence. This strategic framework enhances organizational effectiveness by improving employee performance and capability. Human resource development develops the workforce by facilitating career development and employee training. As such, it is a critical contributor to the overall organizational performance. Specifically, the framework guides organizations on the best strategies, activities, benefits, and opportunities to enhance employee knowledge, experience, and capabilities. Examples of opportunities, activities, and benefits included in human resource development are mentoring programs, tuition, employee coaching, and performance management. The underlying aspects of development programs focus on creating a superior workforce. This approach allows individuals and the organization at large to accomplish set goals and objectives. Notably, companies have numerous internal and external opportunities to develop and improve their workforce. These opportunities may involve informal learning such as collaboration with highly

trained professionals, mentorship programs by highly experienced members, and manager coaching. Alternatively, the strategies can be formal, such as pursuing college courses, implementing organizational change, classroom sessions, and training by consultants or staff. HR professionals focus on three primary aspects of human resource development in the HR life cycle:

1. Training and development – improving knowledge and skills necessary for a future role or responsibilities
2. Organization development – improving organizational effectiveness and well-being through macro and micro changes
3. Career development – improving individual career planning and management through mentorship.

Five Key Functions of Human Resource Development

1. Strategic talent sourcing and acquisition. ...
2. Education-oriented employee benefits. ...
3. Performance measurement and management. ...
4. Formal learning and development programs. ...
5. Internal mobility and succession planning

Human Resource Development Systems – Strategies & Solutions

Scope Of The Study:-

The study is extensive and systematic. The data gathered from the information has been created to a conclusion. The goal of the work centres' completely around human asset rehearses in the chose automobile industry. The methodology of the study has been made with the perspective on the representatives of automobile industry situated in Pithampur in Dhar district.

Review of Literature: -

Mehta (2016) in their research entitled -literature review on HR practices in banking sector. There was a requirement to advance competencies i.e. skill, knowledge and approach among the bank employees to make them more appropriate to the altering circumstances. Since every human being had potential to do remarkable things and to support him to understand, develop and utilize his/her potential, And this was possible only if efficient and effective Human Resource Practices.

Chandra Sinha (2015) "The impact of E-HRM: a study of select Indian organization" researcher investigated that contribution of E-HRM financially is very difficult as implementation and operations of E-HRM is one of the important activities in which business solutions so difficult among different functions. As per the previous studies found that the use of E-HRM was focused by employees' is highly determined the level of usefulness to HR function rather than easiness to use. It has been revealed that e learning for employees' is must require for the employee self-service (ESS) and manager self-service (MSS). Administration of HR function and the deployment of the intranet and extranet in the field of recruitment being the main fields of EHRM, that are facilitated by the E-HRM. The best contribution of E-HRM was found in knowledge management as it facilitates compilation and dissemination of explicit and implicit knowledge very effectively and efficiently. The change in workforce is hard nut to crack, but EHRM has been a harbinger of change management.

Asha Nagendra (2014)"Human Resource Information Systems (HRIS) in HR planning and development in mid to large sized organizations"theauthors highlighted in their research about HR executive's efficiency and awareness about technological phenomenon in organization. The research also found that HR executives well aware that they can increase the efficiency of HR planning through Information technology, saving time and cost. If the implemented technological operation it adds strategic value and competitive advantage for documentation and strategic decision purpose. HR executives believed that managers can find detailed training and relevant for the situation in an organization and employees' development.

Sometime this required subsystem to avoid unnecessary malfunction in the execution and documentation. Organization must synchronize the business function with the relevant information technology.

Sangeeta Trehan and Karan Setia(2014), In their research entitled —Human Resource Management Practices and Organizational Performance: An Indian PerspectiveI give a better understanding of the role of human resource practices in creating and sustaining organizational performance, specifically in the Indian context. They discuss a framework that indicates how external and internal factors affect HRM practices which in turn generate core benefits for the organization and ultimately lead to overall corporate performance. After a comprehensive literature review they highlight three sets of HR practices that would support a healthy and innovation-oriented HR system. They are: (1) training-focused; (2) performance based reward (3) team development. HR Practices in their model refer to these three bundles of practices. OP outcomes are the ultimate dependent variables in the model. They found highly positive relationship between human resource practices and organizational performance.

Objectives Of The Study:-

1. To explore the different HRD climates prevailing among different levels of management in the organization and to identify the influence of HRD elements on HRD climate.
2. To study the relationship among HRD climate, HRD mechanism and effectiveness variables and their inter-effect to bring out the efficiency factors in the organization.

Hypotheses Of The Study:-

1. Different levels of management are independent of different HRD elements.
2. There is no significant impact of elements of HRD on the HRD climate.
3. HRD climate is independent of efficiency of the organizations.

Methodlogy:-

The opinion of the respondents may be raised. The data were collected only on current employees not to an employee who left the organization. The study was restricted to the areas of Dhār district. The complete analysis was done using statistical tools which has its own limitation. The following research methods were applied: a scientific literature review, interview, comparative data analysis. The collected data was organized in the required form and analysed to get the results out of it. The data has been analysed using IBM SPSS 20.0 statistical software.

Sample and Sample Size:-

For each and every type of research, the researcher needed certain tools and techniques to gather the required information. In the present study, the

investigator used the handmade questionnaire. A questionnaire was developed for collection of primary data among Automobile private sectors employees in Pithampur, Dhar district. The two private sector organizations Eicher Motors & Force Motors have been selected for the present study. The organizations selected are such as consider their human resources as most vulnerable and accordingly emphasize on their HRD programmes. As the study is based on the two management levels top, and middle, the executives are selected as samples in Eicher Motors & Force Motors. A sample of 75 persons was chosen at random. It includes two cadres of employees.

Statistical Tool:-

The demographic variables Age, Salary, Educational Qualification, and Total Experience are introduced in the questionnaire. For all the two executives one is asked to express their opinions about management policy, potential appraisal and organizational development. The questionnaire for middle level management comprises regarding the HRD elements, goal setting, role analysis, performance appraisal, career planning, and executive development. These personal interviews gave useful and perfect information for further statistical analysis.

Analysis And Interpretation:-

Table No. 01 Difference in the Mean scores of three HRD subsystems of top level executives in Eicher & Force Motors.

Management Policy

Category	N	Mean	SD	t value	P value
Eicher Motors	45	24.33	2.84	1.6129	0.1111
Force Motors	30	23.21	3.10		

The T-test for the difference between sample means X_1 & X_2 is exploited here to find the significant difference in means of the scores of management policy of Eicher Motors & Force Motors. The result of T-test ($t = 1.6129$) reveals that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of Eicher & Force Motors on management policy. Both the company executives are same in the view of management's policy on introducing HRD ($P > 0.05$).

Potential Appraisal

Category	N	Mean	SD	t value	P value
Eicher Motors	45	22.65	2.08	1.3835	0.1707
Force Motors	30	21.92	2.46		

From the above table it is found that there is no significant difference in mean scores of potential appraisal of Eicher Motors & Force Motors ($P > 0.05$).

Organizational Development

Category	N	Mean	SD	t value	P value
EICHER MOTORS	45	21.85	1.96	1.1546	0.2520
FORCE MOTORS	30	22.40	2.11		

From the above table it is found that there is no significant difference in mean scores of OD in Eicher Motors & Force Motors. So it is ascertained that the top executives in these private enterprises Eicher & Force Motors are of the same view about the three top levels, HRD elements ($P > 0.05$).

Table No. 02 9. Difference in the Mean Scores of HRD Climate in Eicher & Force Motors.

Category	N	Mean	SD	t value	P value
Eicher Motors	45	29.44	3.31	0.9711	0.3347
Force Motors	30	30.26	3.96		

There is no significant difference in the mean scores of HRD climate in Eicher Motors & Force Motors. So it is concluded that the top level executives in Eicher & Force Motors realized the effectiveness directly builds the HRD climate and the climate is favourable to them ($P > 0.05$).

Table No. 03 6. Difference in the Mean Scores of Individual Efficiency, Organizational Efficiency, Productivity and Environmental Changes

Individual Efficiency					
Category	N	Mean	SD	t value	P value
EICHER MOTORS	45	19.72	2.55	1.4748	0.1446
FORCE MOTORS	30	18.75	3.12		

There is no significant difference between mean scores of Eicher Motors & Force Motors in Individual efficiency ($P > 0.05$)

Organizational Efficiency

Category	N	Mean	SD	t value	P value
EICHER MOTORS	45	23.28	3.27	1.3176	0.1488
FORCE MOTORS	30	24.31	2.52		

There is no significant difference between mean scores of Eicher Motors & Force Motors in organizational efficiency ($P > 0.05$).

Productivity

Category	N	Mean	SD	t value	P value
EICHER MOTORS	45	22.66	2.69	1.4741	0.1448
FORCE MOTORS	30	23.49	1.84		

There is no significant difference in the mean scores of Eicher Motors & Force Motors in productivity ($P > 0.05$).

Environmental Changes

Category	N	Mean	SD	t value	P value
EICHER MOTORS	45	25.30	2.88	1.2202	0.2263
FORCE MOTORS	30	26.04	2.02		

There is no significant difference in the mean scores of Eicher Motors & Force Motors in environmental changes. So on the whole, it is concluded that the top level executives of Eicher & Force Motors are of the same view that HRD practices increased IE, OE, PDY and ENC significantly ($P > 0.05$).

Table No. 04 8. Difference between Mean Scores of effectiveness variables of middle level management in Eicher & Force Motors

Individual Efficiency					
Category	N	Mean	SD	t value	P value
EICHER MOTORS	45	27.19	3.45	1.3209	0.1907
FORCE MOTORS	30	28.31	3.81		

So there is no significant difference between mean scores of individual efficiency in Eicher Motors & Force Motors ($P > 0.05$).

Organizational Efficiency

Category	N	Mean	SD	t value	P value
EICHER MOTORS	45	24.11	3.66	1.4734	0.1449
FORCE MOTORS	30	23.04	1.89		

There is no significant difference between mean scores of Organizational Efficiency in Eicher Motors & Force Motors ($P > 0.05$).

Productivity

Category	N	Mean	SD	t value	P value
EICHER MOTORS	45	20.44	2.43	1.6059	0.1126
FORCE MOTORS	30	21.51	3.34		

There is no significant difference between mean scores of productivity in Eicher Motors & Force Motors ($P > 0.05$).

Environmental Changes

Category	N	Mean	SD	t value	P value
EICHER MOTORS	45	25.62	1.72	1.4001	0.1657
FORCE MOTORS	30	26.30	2.49		

There is no significant difference between mean scores of environmental changes in Eicher Motors & Force Motors ($P > 0.05$).

Table No. 05 13. Difference between Mean Scores of Climate of Middle level Management in Eicher & Force Motors

Category	N	Mean	SD	t value	P value
EICHER MOTORS	45	28.27	2.74	1.4369	0.1550
FORCE MOTORS	30	29.13	2.20		

There is no significant difference between mean scores of climate of middle level management in Eicher Motors & Force Motors ($P > 0.05$).

Table No. 06 Comparing the Means of the Scores of HRD Elements in Eicher & Force Motors

Goal Setting

Category	N	Mean	SD	t value	P value
EICHER MOTORS	45	24.55	3.21	1.2102	0.2301
FORCE MOTORS	30	23.68	2.79		

The t-test for the difference between sample means X_1 and X_2 is exploited here to find the significant difference in means of the scores of Goal setting in Eicher & Force Motors. It is found there is no significant difference between mean scores of Goal-setting in Eicher Motors & Force Motors ($P > 0.05$).

Role Analysis

Category	N	Mean	SD	t value	P value
EICHER MOTORS	45	21.34	1.79	1.7420	0.0857
FORCE MOTORS	30	20.70	1.12		

There is no significant difference between mean scores of role analysis in Eicher Motors & Force Motors ($P > 0.05$).

Career Planning

Category	N	Mean	SD	t value	P value
EICHER MOTORS	45	23.80	2.42	1.6227	0.1090
FORCE MOTORS	30	22.94	1.96		

There is no significant difference between mean scores of career planning in Eicher Motors & Force Motors ($P > 0.05$).

Executive Development

Category	N	Mean	SD	t value	P value
EICHER MOTORS	45	26.31	3.22	0.8061	0.4228
FORCE MOTORS	30	26.89	2.78		

There is no significant difference between mean scores of Executive Development in Eicher Motors & Force Motors ($P > 0.05$).

Performance Appraisal

Category	N	Mean	SD	t value	P value
EICHER MOTORS	45	21.65	3.03	1.2631	0.2106
FORCE MOTORS	30	22.51	2.66		

There is no significant difference between mean scores of performance appraisal in Eicher Motors & Force Motors. So from the above analysis using parametric t test it is found that Eicher & Force Motors are equal in HRD practices in middle management level ($P > 0.05$).

Findings:-

Human Resources Development in an organization is an integrated and collective form of practice among all levels of management. It helps all sorts of employees to acquire and sharpen the skills to perform their present and future roles, enables them to utilize their inner potential and develop better environmental conditions.

1. HRD programme needs the overall efforts of each and every employee in the form of its sub systems and processes. The study confirmed that the HRD subsystems like management policy on HRD, potential appraisal and Organizational Development (OD) in the top level management, goal setting, role analysis, performance appraisal, career planning and executive development for the middle level management.
2. Eicher Motors & Force Motors the top level executives expressed same views on implementing HRD elements as management

policy, potential appraisal and organizational development for HRD practice. Both the private sector organizations they provide equal importance to potential appraisal and organizational development.

3. It is found that in Eicher Motors & Force Motors the top level executives are of the view that MGMT, POAPL, OD are important subsystems of HRD to increase individual efficiencies, organizational efficiency, productivity and environmental change. The top executives of these private sector organizations are aware of HRD practices and their effect on the overall development of the organization.
4. In the two private sector organizations Eicher Motors & Force Motors the top level executives possess same view on HRD practices and its effects. They feel equally HRD practices in their respective organizations increase individual efficiency, organizational efficiency, productivity and environmental change equally.
5. In both the private sector organizations the middle level executives are enthusiastic in HRD practices. They feel that the HRD subsystems, goal setting, role analysis, career planning, performance appraisal and executive development are equal weightage in the developmental activities. There is no significant difference between middle level executives of Eicher Motors & Force Motors in considering the importance of HRD subsystems.
6. In Eicher Motors & Force Motors it is found that there is no significant difference in the views of middle level executives in the mean scores of effectiveness variables. They profoundly express that the effectiveness variables are equally important for an organization to achieve its goals.
7. In Eicher Motors & Force Motors the middle level executives are of the opinion that the effectiveness variables individual efficiency, organizational efficiency, productivity and environmental change are fundamental building blocks for climate in an organization. The effectiveness variables are highly significant in creating positive impact on the developmental activities due to HRD practice.
8. The HRD practices among middle level executives in the form of goal setting, role analysis, performance appraisal, career planning and executive development in turn creates effectiveness variables and these effectiveness variables built the climate. In Eicher Motors & Force Motors these effectiveness variables are playing significant role in building the climate. It is found that there is significant difference between the opinions of middle level executives about the usefulness of effectiveness variables

in building a conducive, productive climate suitable for smooth relationship among all level executives of management.

Limitations Of The Study:-

1. Many elements of HRD for the three different management levels are difficult to measure and the responses are based on the report of the executives, the executives may sometimes feel that would reveal their performance indirectly.
2. Only nine HRD elements are concentrated for the respective three different level executives. A special care is taken to bring the impact of HRD in the form of limited number of specified variables.
3. All data were collected from the two different organizations Eicher Motors & Force Motors. A broad generalization of the results obtained may not hold good for all the organization in the state or country.
4. The limited number of 75 samples from the three organizations is sorted out for the response and the respondents are allowed to give the response according to their discretion.

Conclusion:-

1. The top level executives are very much enthusiastic in implementing the HRD elements, management policy in favour of HRD, potential appraisal and organizational development for the smooth conduct of organization.
2. Top level executives profoundly implementing HRD in the organization to accrue the benefits in the form of individual efficiency, organizational efficiency, productivity and environmental change.
3. OD and POAPL are introduced and correlated with themselves in a moderate way to implement HRD practices at the top management level.
4. In Eicher & Force Motors the top level executives are of the same opinion in HRD practices and both the top managements expect same sort of results out of HRD practices.
5. Due to HRD practices at the top level executive management, the two private sector organizations realized a considerable change in the climate. There is no significant difference between the nature of existing constructive climate between Eicher & Force Motors.
6. The goal setting is equally popular in both Eicher & Force Motors The middle level executives consult with their superiors while they set goals for themselves.
7. There is a positive impact of goal setting role analysis, performance appraisal, career planning and executive development on individual efficiency, organizational efficiency and productivity and general changes in the climate.

8. The HRD climate is reasonably good and flourishing at the middle management level due to the practice of HRD subsystems.
9. There is lack of integration among all the HRD elements of middle management level in the two public sector organizations.

Suggestions:

1. The HRD department should organize classes, debates, panel discussions etc. to create a view among the executives that HRD is an integrated system meant for everyone in an organization.
2. Top level management's policy should integrate both potential appraisal and organizational development simultaneously.
3. The top management should invest more on strengthening the HRD practices among all level executives.
4. The efforts must be made by the HR departments to restructure all the HRD elements to generate sense of responsibility among all the executives.

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